

BUSINESS ETHICS, JOB SATISFACTION, AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT IN GOVERNMENT-OWNED AIRPORTS IN THAILAND

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Abstract

The objectives of this study were twofold: (a) to assess the current business ethics climate through managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment from the perspectives of employees within the government-owned airports in Thailand, and (b) to provide the information to the airport management to get a better understanding and to identify an appropriate strategy in order to improve working ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment of their employees. Seven indicators of the managerial ethics variable were selected. These indicators consist of Good Citizenship, Integrity, Courage, Common Interest, Determination, Fairness, and Role Model. The five indicators of employees' job satisfaction were based on the common characteristics of job satisfaction identified, including Salary, Promotion, Co-workers, Supervisors, and the Job itself. The three indicators of employees' commitment were based on the common theme, which consists of Affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment, and Normative Commitment. Perceptions of the 15 indicators were collected by utilizing a questionnaire with a five-point Likert-type scale. The sample was 318 employees within the selected 26 government-owned airports of the Department of Airport of Thailand. Descriptive and correlational statistics were used to analyze the collected data. The relationship between socio-demographic profile, managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment was determined. The results suggested valuable insight into the managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment of the organization. Overall, the employees shared a generally high positive opinion of their managerial ethics and had a positive perception of their job satisfaction. For organizational commitment, overall, the employees showed their commitment as neutral. There was a different level of relationship between each of the indicators of managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment. All significant correlation identified was positive, in which the higher level of managerial ethics of the head/supervisors/managers, the employees most likely to have better job satisfaction and organizational commitment in the government-owned airports.

Keywords: Business Ethics, Managerial Ethics, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Government Airports.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the globalized world, corporate fraud and unethical problems have highlighted the necessity of business ethics in a business organization. There is a demand for business ethics and social responsibilities, in which exercising ethical practices has become a core competency that businesses use to gain competitive advantages (Nguyen, Lee, Mujtaba, & Silanont, 2014). The increase in complexity of ethical situations in doing business involves a wide range of relevant ethical issues, including legal protection, human and employee rights, stakeholder expectation, fair competition, and corporate social responsibility (Koh & Boo, 2001). These ethical issues affect parties involved in business, such as employees, customers, competitors, and the general public.

Thailand is facing certain challenges related to ethics in the public sector, including the executive or senior management level, demonstrating a lack of commitment to ethical leadership. In addition, the results of the survey of the commitment index of government agencies in Thailand, conducted by the Office of the Civil Service Commission (2020), found that there are work-related commitment factors, including benefits, compensation, career advancement, personnel development, and evaluation and appointment system indicators, in which government employees have shown a lower commitment. Although many research studies have been conducted recently to explore personal business ethics of workforce, organizational commitment, and employee satisfaction in several business areas in Thailand (e.g., Mujtaba, Cavico & Sungkhawan, 2011; Ngamchokchaicharoen, 2003; Nguyen, Lee, Mujtaba, & Silanont, 2014; Ritthiboon & Boonlua, 2018), there is no valuable study available in the literature that measures business ethics to job satisfaction and organizational commitment of employees in an airport business sector in Thailand. Therefore, an attempt was made to examine the relationship between business ethics (through managerial ethics) and job satisfaction and organizational commitment in the government-owned airports in Thailand through their employees' perceptions.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Ethics

Defining of Ethics

According to Northhouse (2018), "ethics" derives from the Greek word "ethos," which means "customs," "behavior," or "character." In addition, he indicated that ethics include values, morality, virtue, and motivations that an individual or community deems desirable or proper. According to Ghillyer's (2011) study, on the other hand, ethics is the study of how we try to live our lives according to a standard of right or incorrect behavior in how we think and behave toward others and how we would like others to think and behave toward us. Meanwhile, according to Northhouse (2018), the ethical theory provides a framework of rules or principles that help us in making decisions about what is right or wrong and good or bad in a particular scenario.

Leaders' Conduct Theory

There are two ethical theories that deal with the behavior of leaders: the consequences of leaders' actions and the duty or rules governing leaders' actions. The theory of consequences of leaders' actions, or "*Teleological Theory*," applies three distinct approaches to decide what is moral behavior: (a) ethical egoism, (b) utilitarianism, and (c) altruism. The notion of duty or the norms that govern leaders' activities, also known as "*Deontological Theory*," focuses on a leader's acts, obligations, and responsibilities to do the right thing. In this theory, individual actions are ethical when considering both consequences (teleological) and whether the action itself is good.

Leaders' Character Theory

The theory of leaders' character, often known as virtue-based theory," focuses on who leaders are as individuals. Virtue ethics is a moral theory that is contrasted with "deontological theory." Virtue ethics determine the right thing to do based on whatever a virtuous person, a person whose character traits are virtuous and has no vices, would do (Sakellariouv, 2015). These character traits encompass traits such as honesty, kindness, and generosity, which are positively valued in a person. (Sakellariouv, 2015). Hursthouse and Pettigrove (2022) distinguish four types of virtue ethics including of Eudaimonist Virtue Ethics, Agent-Based and Exemplarist Virtue Ethics, Target-Centered Virtue Ethics, and Platonistic Virtue Ethics.

2.2 Ethics and Management

Organization management deals with moral dilemmas on a daily basis. It rarely confronts a decision that is without an ethical component or aspect. Managers deal with ethical issues while they are carrying out their leadership tasks, including dealing with ethical aspects in making decisions (Carroll, 2007). Ethics and management are linked together because an organization's responsibility to be ethical is relied on managers who understand the organization's goals or objectives and drive the attention of employees toward ethics (Arshad, 2016). Management tasks involve planning, organizing, motivating, communicating, and some other management responsibilities which managers must deal with the fact that issues of right and wrong, fairness and unfairness, justice or lack of justice enter into their decisions, actions, or behavior regardless of whether they are involved in (Carroll, 2007). In an organization that is managed in an ethical manner, managers are likely to be distinguished by a sound moral culture, in which decision-making by managers and workers is socially responsible rather than focusing on profits (Amos, 2012). As managers are ones who responsible for both daily business decision-making and business ethics practiced in an organization, ethical behavior has always been a concern, and so it is a demand for effective managers with the ability to behave ethically and to make the right decision (Bulog & Grančić, 2017).

2.3 Ethics in Business

In a modern business environment, companies may focus on making profits over ethical behavior, so it is crucial to realize the importance of understanding ethical behavior (Bulog & Grančić, 2017). Amos (2012) defined business ethics as the behavior that a company follows in its daily interactions with the outside world, considering ethics in a business environment. Furthermore, Byars and Stanberry (2018) described business ethics as the behavior of organizations and their agents in which they follow the law and respect the rights of their stakeholders, particularly their customers, clients, employees, and the surrounding community and environment. As a function of culture, business ethics is changed over time by a driving force of ethical change to advance ethical practices, such as technology (e.g., industrial revolution, mercantilism, postindustrial era, and the information age) and influences outside the industry (e.g., government regulation and consumer pressure) (Byars & Stanberry, 2018).

Good business ethics brings benefits to business organizations in this modern day in both tangible and intangible benefits, such as goodwill, competitive edge, profit maximization,

competitive edge, and corporate growth (Amos, 2012). A business' ethical behavior benefits all of the company's stakeholders, which also, in turn, increases a business's goodwill and reputation that supports profitability (Byars & Stanberry, 2018).

2.4 Codes of Ethics

Codes of ethics is a written standardized ideal of expected behavior patterns for managers and employees of companies that provides guidelines for interactions among companies, community, and other stakeholders through products, services, sales force, marketing communications, and investments, which influence company reputation and overall marketing performance (Andrade, Hamza, & Brasil, 2017). According to Calderón, Ferrero, and Redin (2012), business codes of ethics can be defined as a set of written formal documents of moral standards, corporate rules and principles of conduct, and company philosophy concerning the responsibility of a company to stakeholders, which is used to guide corporates and employees' behavior. Singh and Prasad (2017) indicated five key components of codes of ethics in business organizations including of Values, Principles, Management Support, Personal Responsibility, and Compliance.

2.5 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is employees' attitudes shown toward their work. This attitude comes from the perception of employees about their work. Job satisfaction plays an important role as a factor in evaluating organizational health. Job satisfaction can be defined as "an evaluating process, in which what the person has in front of what he wants is investigated" (Taghizadeh, Moghadam, Yasrebdoost, & Razmi, 2013, p. 56). As job satisfaction is about an individual's attitude, behavior, and views in carrying out work, so job satisfaction is different among employees and will affect the work done by employees. Although limited empirical evidence supports a relationship between ethics and job satisfaction, many research studies find that there is a significant positive relationship between work ethics and job satisfaction (e.g., Al-Nashash, Panigrahi, & Darun, 2018; Monga-Mitonga, 2018; Panigrahi & Al-Nashash, 2019). Among those research studies, although various indicators of job satisfaction have been used depending on the emphasis of researchers, the five common characteristics of job satisfaction are identified, including Pay, Promotion, Co-workers, Supervision, and Job Itself.

2.6 Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment, as described by Porter, Steers, Mowday, and Boulian (1974), is the degree to which an individual identifies with and involvement in a particular organization. Further, they termed commitment is defined by three aspects: a strong belief in and acceptance of the organization's goals and ideals, a readiness to exert significant work on behalf of the organization, and a clear desire to continue membership in the organization. Although there are various definitions of organizational commitment, Meyer and Allen (1991) gave the three common themes of organizational commitment including of Affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment, and Normative Commitment.

2.7 Conceptual Framework

Based on the review of literature, ethical leadership theories, and the frameworks of leaders' ethics and job satisfaction, and organizational commitment, this study develops a relationship between leaders' ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment framework, as shown in Figure 1 and the study's conceptual framework is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Relationship Framework

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The research approach used for this study is quantitative. Descriptive and correlational methods are used to analyze data collected by the questionnaire. Selected indicators of managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment are measured, described, and analyzed to provide valuable information for understanding the current managerial ethical climate, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment within the organization.

3.2 Research Locale and Sampling Procedures

The research is mainly concerned with managerial ethics in public use airports under the administration of the Department of Airport (DOA) and organizational commitment and job satisfaction as perceived by employees. The population for this study is all permanent airport employees in government-owned airports of the DOA. Currently, there are 29 government-owned airports operated by the DOA covering all regions throughout Thailand. According to Raosoft (2004), the minimum recommended random sample size of the survey is 318 with a level of certainty of 95% and an error margin of 5%, and a population of 1,821.

Sampling Framework

Twenty-six airports out of 29 government-owned airports in Thailand are selected. This selection is based on the criteria by taking into account the operational conditions. Although the DOA operates 29 airports in Thailand, there are 26 airports that serve scheduled flights. The criteria for a sampling framework are those government-owned airports that are open to public use and accommodate scheduled flight operations.

Sampling Procedures

Because of time and resource limitations, geographical limitations, and the situation of COVID-19 outbreak in Thailand, this study uses a non-probability purposive sampling technique to select a sampling group. The respondents from all departments at each airport are purposely selected to represent the employee. Then, the study used voluntary sampling in which employees in a sampling group voluntarily participate in a survey (self-selected).

3.3 Scope and Delimitation

This study included only airport employees of the DOA-Thailand who are working at 26 airports. The evaluation of the employees' perceptions toward managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment is administered by using a questionnaire, and no attempt is made for interviews. Many definitions of the concept of ethics exist, depending on researchers' emphases, and this study defines the term leader or managerial ethical climate as perceptions that employees share about their ethical leadership in terms of leaders' conduct and leaders' character.

Due to time and geographical limitations and the situation of COVID-19, the survey instrument is electronically distributed and collected for return to the researcher. The self-reported method was used because of the limitations of data collection constructs. The study is conducted over

a limited period of time, which may affect the results of the study depending on working conditions occurring during that time. It is assumed that the respondents answer the survey questions truthfully.

3.4 Research Instrument

The questionnaire was used to collect information and data on the current circumstance and to make inquiries about current employees' attitudes, beliefs, and opinions toward the subject of the study. The questionnaire comprised four segments that includes a checklist, open-ended questions, and Likert-type questions. The Likert scale questions are used to evaluate the perceptions of airport employees concerning the leaders' ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment indicators.

The Likert scale questionnaire contains 27 questions (ET1 to ET27) attempting to measure employees' perceptions toward the indicators of managerial ethics. These questions are developed based on the seven core principles of the codes of ethics stipulated in the Ethical Standard Act B.E. 2562 (2019) including Good Citizenship, Integrity, Courage, Common Interest, Determination, Fairness, and Role Model. The 17 questions (JS1 to JS17) are developed attempting to measure employees' perceptions toward the indicators of job satisfaction. These questions are developed based on the five indicators of job satisfaction based on the common characteristics of job satisfaction comprising Pay, Promotion, Co-workers, Supervisors, and the Job itself. The 18 questions (OC1 to OC18) are developed attempting to measure employees' perceptions toward the indicators of organizational commitment. These questions are developed based on common themes of organizational commitment of Mayer and Allen (1991), which include Affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment, and Normative Commitment. The study has adopted a shortened version of the most accepted questionnaire to measure the organizational commitment of Mayer and Allen (1991).

3.5 Data Gathering Procedure

In gathering data for this research, the questionnaire has gone through several important stages, such as translation, validating, and administration of the questionnaire in terms of distribution and response. Due to time and geographical limitations and COVID-19 outbreak situation in Thailand, the questionnaire is converted to Google Form online survey and delivered by sending a request letter attached with a QR code to conduct survey to the Director of each selected government airport to participate in the online survey.

3.6 Data Management and Analysis

Statistical Analysis

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was utilized as a tool for organizing and analyzing data.

The following statistical analyses are conducted utilizing SPSS:

- a) Demographic information of the participants is analyzed using SPSS to determine their frequencies;
- b) Responses to the ethics scale, job satisfaction scale, and organizational commitment scale are analyzed to determine their factor structures and reliabilities of the scales; and
- c) SPSS is used to analyze the correlation among gender, age, years of experience, managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment in order to detect any multicollinearity of variables.

Data Collection Device

Instrument Reliability. The internal consistency reliability of the questionnaire was assessed to determine consistency among questions. A Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis is performed to ensure that data gathered by the questionnaire are consistent and had inter-item reliability.

Instrument Validity. The content and construct validity of the instrument are provided to guarantee that the study's conclusion satisfied its aims. The definition of each construct and concept is well defined before developing the questionnaire. The questionnaire is carefully designed to reflect the research objectives and constructs that the study attempts to measure. A review of the relevant literature is necessary in order to define the definitions of constructs. The constructs related to managerial ethics are defined based on the Thai Ethical Standard Act B.E. 2562 (2019). The constructs related to job satisfaction are defined based on the common characteristics of job satisfaction identified within the review of relevant pieces of literature. The constructs related to organizational commitment are defined based on the study of Meyer and Allen (1991).

Treatment of the Data

Data gathered from the questionnaires were treated in two separate parts due to the nature of data types. The first part is basic personal information: gender, age, education, years of experience, and monthly salary. The second part is perception data based on the managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment factors. These collected data are analyzed by using the SPSS software. Perception scores for the participants on each of the constructs of managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment are determined by calculating the mean of the participants' responses to the questions in each construct section. This mean score represents the overall status of the respondents' perception of the organization's managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment concerning each construct.

Reliability Testing

Cronbach's alpha internal consistency test was used to examine the reliability of collected data. The consistency of respondents is evaluated by using the questions in each indicator. Questions ET1 to ET27 are used for testing Cronbach's alpha of the Managerial Ethics survey. Questions JS1 to JS17 are used for testing Cronbach's alpha of the Job Satisfaction survey. Questions OC1 to OC18 are used for testing Cronbach's alpha of the Organizational Commitment survey.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Research Question 1. The research question stated that “how may the socio – demographic profile of the respondents be described in terms of gender, age, number of years in service, level of education, and monthly salary?”

The demographic profile of 318 respondents showed that the majority of respondents were male (53.46%), while the remainders were female (46.54%). The highest percentage of respondents was between the age of 30 to 39 years old, which accounted for 41.82%. The highest percentage of the number of years in service of the respondents in the airports was not more than five years, which accounted for 58.18%. The highest percentage of respondents’ monthly salary ranged from 10,000 to 19,999 baht, which was 70.13%. The highest percentage of respondents’ level of education was a bachelor’s degree, which was 70.13%.

Research Question 2. The research question stated that “how may the managerial ethics of the head/supervisors/managers be described by the respondents in terms of good citizenship, integrity, courage, common interest, determination, fairness, and role model?”

Overall, the employees of government–owned airports showed a high positive level of perception of managerial ethics of the head/supervisors/managers in terms of good citizenship, integrity, courage, common interest, determination, and role model. They seemed to disagree in terms of the fairness of their head/supervisors/managers in performing duties by making decisions based on relationship and socioeconomic status.

Research Question 3. The research question stated that “how may the job satisfaction of the respondents be described in terms of pay, promotion, co–workers, supervisors, and job – itself?”

Overall, the employees of government–owned airports showed a good positive level of perception of their job satisfaction in terms of promotion, co – workers, supervisors, and the job – itself. They seemed to show a neutral perception in terms of the pay indicator. This reflected low satisfaction of the employees on benefits, compensation, and incentive system provided by the organization.

Research Question 4. The research question stated that “how may the organizational commitment of the respondents be described in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment?”

Overall, the employees of government–owned airports showed a good positive level of perception of their organizational commitment in terms of affective commitment. They seemed to show a neutral perception of continuance commitment and normative commitment. This reflected how the employees perceived the costs associated with leaving the organization and how they felt obligated to remain and to continue employment with the organization.

Research Question 5. The research question stated that “Is there a significant relationship between socio–demographic profile and managerial ethics of head/supervisors/ managers; socio – demographic profile and job satisfaction; and socio – demographic profile and organizational commitment?”

The relationship between socio–demographic profile and managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers is as followings:

1. The gender of the respondents was positively correlated with the managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers in terms of integrity, courage, common interest, determination, fairness, and role model. There was no relationship between gender and managerial ethics in terms of good citizenship.
2. The age of the respondents was positively correlated with the managerial ethics of the head/supervisors/managers in terms of good citizenship. There was no relationship between age and managerial ethics in terms of integrity, courage, common interest, determination, fairness, and role model.
3. The years of experience of the respondents were positively correlated with the managerial ethics of the head/supervisors/managers in terms of good citizenship. There was no relationship between years of experience and managerial ethics in terms of integrity, courage, common interest, determination, fairness, and role model.
4. The level of education of the respondents was positively correlated with the managerial ethics of the head/supervisors/managers in terms of integrity, courage, common interest, determination, fairness, and role model. There was no relationship between the level of education and managerial ethics in terms of good citizenship.
5. The monthly salary of the respondents was positively correlated with the managerial ethics of the head/supervisors/managers in terms of good citizenship, integrity, courage, common interest, determination, fairness, and role model.

The relationship between socio–demographic profile and job satisfaction of the employees is as followings:

1. The gender of the respondents was positively correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of promotion, co – workers, and job – itself. There was no relationship between gender and job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay and supervisors.
2. The age of the respondents was not correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay, promotion, co – workers, supervisors, and the job – itself.
3. The years of experience of the respondents were not correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay, promotion, co – workers, supervisors, and the job – itself.
4. The level of education of the respondents was positively correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay, promotion, co – workers, supervisors, and the job – itself.
5. The monthly salary of the respondents was positively correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay, promotion, and job – itself. There was no relationship between monthly salary and job satisfaction of employees in terms of co – workers and supervisors.

The relationship between the socio–demographic profile and the organizational commitment of the employees is as followings:

1. The gender of the respondents was not correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.
2. The age of the respondents was positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment and normative commitment. There was no relationship between age and organizational commitment of employees in terms of continuance commitment.
3. The years of experience of the respondents were positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment and normative commitment. There was no relationship between years of experience and the organizational commitment of employees in terms of continuance commitment.
4. The level of education of the respondents was not correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.
5. The monthly salary of the respondents was positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment and normative commitment. There was no relationship between monthly salary and organizational commitment of employees in terms of continuance commitment.

Research Question 6. The research question stated that “is there a significant relationship between managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers and job satisfaction; and managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers and organizational commitment?”

The relationship between the managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers and the job satisfaction of the employees is as followings:

1. The managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers in terms of good citizenship were positively correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay, promotion, co–workers, supervisors, and the job–itself.
2. The managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers in terms of integrity were positively correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay, promotion, co–workers, supervisors, and the job–itself.
3. The managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers in terms of courage were positively correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay, promotion, co –workers, supervisors, and the job–itself.
4. The managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers in terms of common interest were positively correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay, promotion, co –workers, supervisors, and the job–itself.

5. The managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers in terms of determination were positively correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay, promotion, co-workers, supervisors, and the job-itself.
6. The managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers in terms of fairness were positively correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay, promotion, co-workers, supervisors, and the job-itself.
7. The managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers in terms of role model was positively correlated with the job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay, promotion, co-workers, supervisors, and the job-itself.

The relationship between the managerial ethics of head/supervisors/managers and the organizational commitment of the employees is as followings:

1. The managerial ethics of heads/supervisors/managers in terms of good citizenship were positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.
2. The managerial ethics of the head/supervisors/managers in terms of integrity were positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment and normative commitment. There was no relationship between integrity and the organizational commitment of employees in terms of continuance commitment.
3. The managerial ethics of heads/supervisors/managers in terms of courage were positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.
4. The managerial ethics of heads/supervisors/managers in terms of common interest were positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.
5. The managerial ethics of the head/supervisors/managers in terms of determination were positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.
6. The managerial ethics of heads/supervisors/managers in terms of fairness were positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment and normative commitment. There was no relationship between fairness and the organizational commitment of employees in terms of continuance commitment.
7. The managerial ethics of heads/supervisors/managers in terms of role models were positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.

Research Question 7. The research question stated that “Is there a significant relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment of the respondents?”

The relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment of the employees is as followings:

1. The job satisfaction of employees in terms of pay was positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.
2. The job satisfaction of employees in terms of promotion was positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment and normative commitment. There was no relationship between promotion and organizational commitment of employees in terms of continuance commitment.
3. The job satisfaction of employees in terms of co-workers was positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.
4. The job satisfaction of employees in terms of supervisors was positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.
5. The job satisfaction of employees in terms of the job-itself was positively correlated with the organizational commitment of employees in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

The results reflected how the employees perceived the behavior of middle- and upper-level management to demonstrate an enduring and positive attitude toward ethical business. It also reflected how middle- and upper-level management provides benefits, compensation, and incentive system within the organization, and how the employees positively feel personally and emotionally involved with and responsible for the success of the organization. Based on the employees' perception, managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment had a positive relationship within the government-owned airports in Thailand. In addition, the contributing factors of gender, age, years of experience, level of education, and monthly salary had effects on the level of relationship between managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment. Thus, managerial ethics within organizations is an important area of business ethics. Ethical managers create a positive working environment leading to the increase of positive relationships between employees' perceptions.

5.2 Recommendations

Managerial ethics, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment can be pivotal in developing and managing business strategy. For improving managerial ethics, employees' job satisfaction, and organizational commitment in the workplace for government-owned airports, the followings are recommendations to the management and policy makers;

First, management may try to understand the ethical climate and its factors in order to increase organizational commitment to their employees. Management can create a positive and desirable ethical climate for employees by emphasizing on management integrity and determination in order to increase employees' normative commitment in terms of responsibility to remain with the organization and try to reach organizational goals.

Second, management may encourage employees to participate in team bonding activities to create emotional attachment and enjoy staying at the organization to increase affective commitment. In addition, management may be familiar with the organizational goals and be committed to achieving them in order to be good examples for employees and to create influence and motivation with their behavior.

Third, management and policy makers may contemplate whether the results of this research study coincide with existing strategies to increase employee commitment and job satisfaction when executing organizational strategies by;

- (a) Enhancing transparency and fairness by ensuring that communication is unambiguous and succinct between the management team and between management and employees allowing for an improved flow of communication from top to bottom and bottom to top in the organization;
- (b) Supporting job promotion opportunity of employees by creating a flexible leadership to allow for management to interact with each employee differently to help find the best strategy to improve the person-organization fit, in which employees are placed in positions that allow them for success, motivation, and satisfaction;
- (c) Implementing an incentive program that recognizes those employees who perform their work exceptionally, which greatly improves and positively influences the organizational atmosphere and work environment;
- (d) Enhancing payment scheme and the employees' benefits by providing lifetime earnings to attract new employees, retain the organizational workforce, and boost productivity for both pay and non-pay, such as health care, mental health services, vacation, retirement, compensation for disabilities, training, and job flexibility; and
- (e) Promoting positive culture and atmosphere by fostering cohesion among management and employees by encouraging employees to participate in team bonding activities, social events, and outings.

References

- 1) Al-Nashash, H. M., Panigrahi, S. K., & Darun M. R. B. (2018). Do work ethics improves employee job satisfaction? Insights from Jordanian banks. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(11), 627 – 645.
- 2) Amos, D. N. (2012). Business ethics: A catalyst for rapid economic growth. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 2(10), 30 – 37.
- 3) Andrade, J., Hamza, K., & Xara-Brasil, D. (2017). Business ethics: International analysis of codes of ethics and conduct. *Brazilian Journal of Marketing – BJM*, 6(1), 1 – 15.
- 4) Arshad, S. H. (2016). The role of the ethics in the management of the organization. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 5(8), 106 –116.
- 5) Bulog, I., & Grančić, I. (2017). The benefits of business ethics - Ethical behavior of decision makers: The empirical findings from Croatia. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(4), 9 –14.
- 6) Byars, S. M., & Stanberry, K. (2018). *Business ethics*. Rice University, Houston, Texas: OpenStax Publications.
- 7) Calderón, R., Ferrero, I., & Redin, D. M. (2012). Ethical codes and corporate responsibility of the most admired companies of the world: Toward a third generation ethics?. *Business and Politics*, 14(4), 1–24.
- 8) CARROLL, A. B. (2007). Ethics in management. *A Companion to Business Ethics*, 141–152. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470998397.CH12>
- 9) Department of Airport. (2021). *Annual Report 2020*. Retrieved from <https://doa.airports.go.th/th/e-magazine/189.html>
- 10) Ethical Standard Act B.E. 2562. (2019). *Royal Thai Government Gazette*. Retrieved from http://www.ratchakitcha.soc.go.th/DATA/PDF/2562/A/050/T_0001.PDF
- 11) Ghillyer, A. (2011). *Business ethics now*. Retrieved from https://home.kku.ac.th/ssuwattana/050221Business%20Ethics/Textbook_PDF/Chapters01-10.pdf
- 12) Hursthouse, R., & Pettigrove, G. (2022). *Virtue Ethics*. The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Winter 2022 Edition). Retrieved from <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/ethics-virtue/#FormVirtEthi>
- 13) Koh, H.C., & Boo, E.H.Y. (2001). The link between organizational ethics and job satisfaction: A study of managers in Singapore. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 29, 309–324. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010741519818>
- 14) Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resources Management Review*, 1(1), 81–89.
- 15) Monga–Mitonga, J. (2018). Ethical climate influences on employee commitment through job satisfaction in a transport sector industry. *Journal of Psychology in Africa*, 28(1), 15 –20.
- 16) Mujtaba, B. G., Cavico, F. J., & Sungkhawan, J. (2011). Business ethics of government employees and future lawyers in Thailand: A study of age, gender, management experience, and education. *International Business Research*, 4(1), 16–27.
- 17) Ngamchokchaicharoen, R. (2003). A study of organizational commitment in Thailand. *ASHRAE Journal*. Retrieved from https://www.ashraethailand.org/download/ashraethailand_org/journal_20022003_02_a%20study%20of%20organizational%20commitment%20in%20thailand.pdf
- 18) Nguyen, D. D. L., Lee, K., Mujtaba, B. G., & Silanont, S. P. (2014). Business ethics perceptions of working adults: A study in Thailand. *International Journal of Asian Business and Information Management*, 5(2), 23 – 40

- 19) Northouse, P. G. (2018). *Leadership theory and practice*. United States of America: SAGE Publications.
- 20) Office of the Civil Service Commission. (2020). Report on the survey of the commitment index of government agencies in Thailand 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.ocsc.go.th/download/2563/engagement-index>
- 21) Panigrahi, S. K., & Al-Nashash, H. M. (2019). Quality work ethics and job satisfaction: An empirical analysis. *Quality Access to Success*, 20(168), 41 – 47.
- 22) Porter, L. W., Steers, R. M., Mowday, R. T., & Boulian, P. V. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59(5), 603 – 609. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0037335>
- 23) Raosoft. (2004). *Raosoft Sample Size Calculator*. Raosoft, Inc., Seattle. <http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>
- 24) Ritthiboon, N., & Boonlua, S. (2018). Factor Influencing organization commitment of staff in the government sectors in North Eastern Thailand. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Rajapruk University*. Retrieved from <https://so03.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/rpu/article/view/191611/133736>
- 25) Sakellariou, A. M. (2015). Virtue ethics and its potential as the leading moral theory. *Discussions*, 12(1). Retrieved from <http://www.inquiriesjournal.com/a?id=1385>
- 26) Singh, C., & Prasad, M. (2017). Code of ethics in an organisation. *International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management (IJAIEM)*, 6(5), 138–142.
- 27) Taghizadeh, H., Moghadam, S. S., Yasrebdoost, H. & Razmi, A. (2013). Evaluation of the relation of business ethics and job satisfaction. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*, 2(8), 56 – 62.